

Geostatistical modelling of mine tailings and comparative analysis of sampling methodologies: A case study of the Otanmäki ilmenite tailings storage facility project

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ABSTRACT

Increasing concerns about the availability of Critical Raw Materials (CRMs) have shifted focus to extractive waste sites as potential sources for secondary resources. Resource assessment requires robust investigation and resource definition, necessitating representative sampling and use of an appropriate modelling method. In this study, spatial sampling sensitivity was tested at the Otanmäki tailings storage facility (TSF) by conducting multiple models at different scales, utilizing both previously collected and new data. Additionally, three tailings sampling methodologies were evaluated to ensure sample representativity and minimize contamination: a tube sampler with a valve, a flow-through blade, and an auger drill.

Results indicated that both the auger drill and the tube sampler perform well and provide similar results under low moisture conditions. However, the tube sampler was estimated to be more accurate in varying conditions, despite it having a smaller sample volume and being more time-consuming to use. According to the modelling results, there were minimal changes in grade and tonnage when increasing sampling density or changes in model scale. Thus, the existing resource estimation from the Otanmäki TSF that was based on a 100 × 100 m grid could be considered as having a high-confidence in relation to the G-category in the United Nations Framework Classification for Resources (UNFC) system with effective investigation of tailings sites requires a tailored approach considering factors such as ore deposit type, mineralization style, and information on ore processing and tailings disposal practices. This work provides insights into tailings resource modelling, estimation confidence, sample representativity, and optimal sampling strategies, aiding in the resource classification of tailings sites.

1. Introduction

The EU's Critical Raw Materials (CRMs) are essential to Europe's economy, forming the backbone of various industries and modern technologies (European Commission, 2024). These materials are crucial for producing e.g., green transition technologies like solar panels, wind turbines, and electric vehicles. Increasing concerns about CRM availability have turned focus to extractive waste sites as secondary resource sources. The Critical Raw Materials Act sets a benchmark that 10 % of CRMs consumed in the EU need to be produced in the EU by 2030, and mandates that by at least 15 % of the EU's annual consumption should come from recycling to help meet this quota (European Commission, 2024). To achieve this, EU countries and private operators should

explore CRM recovery from extractive waste and ideally classify these resources using the United Nations Framework Classification for Resources (UNFC) (UNECE, 2019).

The UNFC is a global standard for the sustainable management of natural resources such as minerals, petroleum, nuclear fuels, anthropogenic resources, renewable energy, geological storage, and groundwater. One of the purposes of the UNFC is to offer a standardized framework for classifying mineral resources and products throughout the project value chain, while also identifying the risks and opportunities associated with various projects (UNECE, 2019, 2022, 2024). UNFC is a generic, principle-based system in which quantities are classified by three fundamental criteria: the social-environmental-economic viability (E-axis), technical feasibility (F-axis) and degree of confidence

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in the estimates (G-axis) (UNECE, 2019). UNFC-based inventories for re-mining of tailings storage facility (TSF) projects is a relatively recent concept. This method has been applied in places like Cabeço do Pião, Portugal and Bollrich, Germany (Suppes and Heuss-Aßbichler, 2021a,b). In these cases, the tailings storage facilities were deemed non-viable projects.

In Finland, around 100 Mt. of extractive waste, i.e. waste rock and tailings, is being produced annually, comprising 74 % of the total amount of all annually produced waste streams (Karlsson et al., 2024). The flotation processing method was introduced in Finland in 1911, and since then, around 500 Mt. of tailings have been produced (Puustinen, 2003). The CRM resource potential bound to Finnish extractive waste seems to be modest, as the concentrations, commonly ranging from 0.002 to 0.2 %, are relatively low compared to conventional ore grades, (Karlsson et al., 2024). On the other hand, the existing Finnish extractive waste data is uncertain due to the limited number of samples from most sites, inadequate analysis methods and indirect estimations of the amount of waste. Contamination is a major source of uncertainty in the resource estimation of tailings as the material consists of unconsolidated sands (Robertson, 1994), highlighting the need for a sample collection method that produces representative samples. So far, only the historic Otanmäki TSF has been recently assessed in more detail and classified according to the UNFC system as a potentially viable project (Hokka and Markovaara-Koivisto, 2019; Eerola et al., 2024).

In the mining industry the economic viability of re-mining of extractive waste sites are assessed through feasibility studies, which take into account the resource estimate of the deposit, as well as various technical, economic, and environmental factors (Modifying Factors) (CRIRSCO Template, 2019). Thus, the assessment of project viability needs robust investigation and resource definition, which in turn requires representative sampling and use of an appropriate modelling method (Karacan et al., 2023). The optimum sampling strategies should always be site specific and assessment of commercial viability of TSF projects should consider several aspects, including the ore deposit type, mineralization style, and information on ore processing and tailings disposal practices (Sädbom and Bäckström, 2018; Blannin et al., 2022). The need for field studies related to suitable geostatistical modelling in tailings deposits to objectively sample and model TSFs has been emphasized (e.g., Lottermoser, 2011; Blannin et al., 2022; Karacan et al., 2023). Understanding the grade and grain size continuity of tailings is essential for robust mineral resource estimates which is critical to assess the future potential for secondary resources in Europe.

The objective of this study was to perform a spatial sampling sensitivity analysis test at a TSF by conducting multiple models (ordinary kriging and inverse distance) at different scales, utilizing previously collected and new data from the Otanmäki TSF. The Otanmäki site, which contains the CRMs titanium (ilmenite) and vanadium, was selected as a case site due to having background data with nominal sample spacing, providing a unique opportunity to investigate the accuracy of the existing resource model. In this study, estimation confidence is reflected via the G-category of the UNFC system, where the G-axis categories represent quantities that can be estimated at a high-level (G1), moderate-level (G2) or low-level (G3) of confidence, or such quantities that are estimated primarily on indirect evidence (G4) (UNECE, 2019). Furthermore, three sampling methodologies were evaluated to ensure good sample representativity and minimize contamination: a tube sampler with a valve, a flow-through blade, and an auger drill. This comparison aimed to identify the most effective sampling tool and assess the comparability of samples collected with different methods. Our study provides insights into tailings resource modelling, estimation confidence, sample representativity and optimal sampling strategy, aiding in the resource classification of tailings re-mining projects.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Target site

The historic Otanmäki mine is located in the municipality of Kajaani in Central Finland, about 30 km SW of the city centre (Fig. 1). The primary Fe-Ti-V deposit was hosted in Paleoproterozoic (2.06 Ga) layered gabbro-anorthosite, containing two ore bodies, Otanmäki and Vuorokas (Sarapää et al., 2015). The main ore minerals were ilmenite and V-rich (0.62 wt% V) magnetite. The Otanmäki underground mine operated from 1953 until 1985 and was exploited down to a level of -675 m (485 m below the sea level), containing 125 km of drive tunnels with three separate shafts: Otanmäki, Suomalmi and Vuorokas (Illi et al., 1985). During the life of mine the Otanmäki mine processed a total of 31 Mt. of V-Ti-Fe ore with grades of 32–34 % Fe, 9–12 % TiO₂, 0.26 % V and some pyrite (FeS₂) as a by-product (Illi et al., 1985; Sarapää et al., 2015). This included 7.6 Mt. of magnetite (Fe₃O₄), 3.8 Mt. of ilmenite (FeTiO₃), 0.2 Mt. of pyrite and 55,545 t of vanadium pentoxide (V₂O₅), which were produced in a processing plant at the site. The process included the separation of magnetite by dry and wet magnetic methods, and the separation of pyrite and ilmenite by flotation methods (Illi et al., 1985). A total of 9.8 Mt. of tailings are deposited in an approximately 145 ha tailings storage facility, located in a natural low-land area (Fig. 1). The basal structure of the facility is peat. The tailings were pumped into the tailings facility via a single discharge outlet located at the southwestern corner of the tailings pond.

The current owner of the Otanmäki mine site, including the TSF, is Otanmäki Mine Oy. The company is interested in starting to produce ilmenite from the tailings and has been investigating the site since 2017. Based on the investigations, the tailings material consists mainly of hastingsite (48 %; NaCa₂Fe₂ + 3Fe₃ + 4Al₂Si₆O₂₂(OH)₂), which is a member of the hornblende group, ilmenite (15 %) and lesser amounts of magnetite, pyrite and silicates including chlorite ((Mg,Fe)₃(Si,Al)₄O₁₀(OH)₂·(Mg,Fe)₃(OH)₆), biotite ((K(Mg,Fe)₃AlSi₃O₁₀(OH,F)₂) and albite (NaAlSi₃O₈) (Makkonen and Lavikko, 2018). Ilmenite has been found to be enriched in the grain size fraction under 32 µm, in which the ilmenite content is around 29 %. However, particle size varies, which can have an effect on the recoverable resources due to the difficulty in processing the fine-grained ilmenite fraction (Hokka and Markovaara-Koivisto, 2019). The material variation is due to primary deposition of the tailings from a single discharge outlet where coarse-grained material is deposited closer to the outlet and fine-grained material further out.

The interim resource estimate for Otanmäki TSF indicated 9.8 Mt. at 7.9 % TiO₂ (16 % FeTiO₃) using 4 % TiO₂ cut-off value (Hokka and Markovaara-Koivisto, 2019). The company's resource estimation is based on a 100 × 100 m grid of 140 drill holes made with an auger drill and an additional 21 hand-dug shallow pits, both conducted in 2017–2018. The company is currently completing its feasibility study and the plan is to start producing ilmenite by the year 2027 (Otanmäki Mine oy website, 2024).

Based on the current information, the Otanmäki TSF project is classified under UNFC as E2, F2, G2, a potentially viable project (Eerola et al., 2024). The mineral company is conducting the Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) which is currently in the program phase. According to Eerola et al. (2024), the environmental and social risks of the project appear to be low, as the tailings is presumed to be non-hazardous, and public acceptance is relatively good.

2.2. Sampling, data collection and QA/QC

A drone photogrammetric survey was carried out in order to create a higher resolution digital elevation model (DEM) of the tailings area (Fig. 2). A Wingtra Gen 1 drone was used with a Sony RX1R (42-megapixel, resolution: 1.6 cm/pixel) camera attached to take the images from a flight altitude of 120 m. The ortho image was based on three

Fig. 1. The Otanmäki tailings storage facility (TSF) is located in central Finland, in the town of Otanmäki, within the municipality of Kajaani. The tailings discharge outlet is marked by a white star and the flow direction by the white arrow. Background map and aerial image (c) National Land Survey of Finland.

separate flights. Several station points were measured around the tailings using differential GPRS to provide accurate digital elevation model.

The sampling at the Otanmäki TSF was conducted in May 2023 and consisted of 233 assay samples collected from 34 new drillholes (including six duplicate holes) at 28 drilling points (Supplementary File 1). The sampling locations were selected based on previous sample points used during 2017–2018, which included 48 sample points and a total of 253 assay samples used also in this study (Fig. 2). A Welch's *t*-test was performed to compare the average grade values of TiO_2 , Fe_2O_3 , and V between the two data sets (2017–2018 and 2023) to ensure that the datasets can be considered to represent a single grade distribution and combined into one database. Nine new drill holes were established in a 25×25 m grid at the centre of four pre-existing sample points within the sampling area. From this central region, sampling was extended in four directions (NW, NE, SE, SW), with samples taken at 50 m intervals, and a final sample at a 100 m interval, resulting in four to five samples per extension. The planned sample points were located using differential GPS (DGPS) and re-measured after drilling commenced. The last sample point on the NW line was relocated 50 m inward due to conditions in the tailings pond, while the final sample point on the SW line was excluded, as it would have entered a different grain size domain (Hokka and Markovaara-Koivisto, 2019). This selection of sample points was designed to facilitate a comparison of results at different sampling densities and to assess their effects on resource modelling outcomes.

The sampling was supervised by geologists from the Geological Survey of Finland (GTK) and carried out by the GTK's light-weight sampling unit (GM-50 drill rig). The samples were collected into a large plastic bag with a tube sampler with a plastic tube and a flapper valve, which has been known to perform well in the Otanmäki tailings material. Samples from the drillholes were taken at 1 m intervals and drilling was continued until the peat layer at the base of the TSF was reached, with the tailings depth ranging between 2.4 m and 9.4 m. The chain of custody was maintained in collaboration with Otanmäki Mine Oy, and the samples were transported to GTK's Kuopio office for storage. Manual sample preparation was used to split the large sample into approximately 2 kg subsamples, which were then stored in a cooler. Prior to submission to the laboratory, another of the two 2 kg subsamples was further divided into two subsamples: one for geochemical analysis and one for grains size distribution analysis. Sample

preparation included initial homogenization to prevent any artificial sorting, scooping a 450-gram geochemical sample into a plastic bag using a plastic scoop, and inserting appropriate labelling and blind sample numbers to all the stored samples.

QC samples were included in the batch sent to the laboratory for assaying at pre-determined intervals following GTK's internal standard operating procedure (Supplementary File 2). QC samples included duplicate samples taken in the field, pulp duplicates, blank samples, and certified reference materials. A total of 49 control samples were inserted into the sample stream, which accounts for 21 % of the samples. The certified reference material (CRM) used in this study was AMIS0368 prepared by African Mineral Standards (AMIS). The material for the CRM originated from the Rhovan Vanadium Mine in South Africa from a vanadium bearing titaniferous magnetite gabbro. The material most closely resembles the Otanmäki-type ore among available certified reference materials regarding ore grade and matrix. The material was sent in 50 g vacuum sealed standard geochemical sachets. The accuracy of the assay results was monitored against average grades and standard deviations of the 14 samples of reference material given by AMIS. The samples used for blanks were Kirami filtered sand with grain size of 0.7–1.4 mm. The purpose of the blank samples is to ensure that there is no cross-contamination between samples and that there are no errors in the sample sequencing (Smee et al., 2024). Since we did not have exact grades of Fe_2O_3 or TiO_2 for the Kirami filtered sand used as blank material, the failure limit for the blank samples indicating contamination is set at $10\times$ the lowest measured grade from the blank samples. The first blank sample was inserted as the first sample in the sample sequence. Field duplicates (14 samples) and pulp duplicates (9 samples) were used to ensure precision in the laboratory's analytical methods and to test the homogeneity of the sample material. The results indicated acceptable accuracy for major and trace elements, with the majority of CRMs returning an error of less than (\pm) three standard deviations from the mean.

2.3. Sampling methodology test

To ensure good sample representativity and minimize contamination, a sampling methodology test was included in the study. Representative sampling is especially important when drilling through

Fig. 2. The Otanmäki tailings pond with the digital elevation model (DEM) and sample points. The red and green dots represent new sample points collected in 2023. The green dots present the sampling methodology test points. The white dots represent old sample points collected in 2017–2018 that were used as background values for the resource modelling in this study. The inset (upper-left corner) is a close up of the sampling configuration in the central part of the sampling area. The different model extents (600 m × 700 m, 300 m × 300 m and 100 m × 100 m) are shown as dotted lines in the upper figures. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

unconsolidated sand with varying moisture content. The test included three types of sampling methods that can be used for loose or unconsolidated materials: 1) tube sampler with a valve, which was also used for the main sampling of this study, 2) flow-through blade, and 3) auger drill, which was utilized in the sampling campaign in 2017–2018. With all methods, the GTK’s GM50 drill rig was utilized. Three drillhole points were used to compare results between sampling methods and differences in repeated drilling at the same point (Fig. 2).

2.3.1. Tube sampler with a plastic tube and a flapper valve

The tube sampler with a valve method involves using a flow-through blade attached to a tube sampler where the sample is collected and retained within a 0.5 m plastic tube (Fig. 3A). A flapper valve or slat shutter at the end of the plastic tube ensures that the sample stays inside the tube during the retrieval phase. This method requires that the sampled material is relatively soft or loose. Before being sent to the laboratory, the 0.5-meter subsamples were combined into 1-meter composite samples.

Fig. 3. Three sampling methodologies were tested at the Otanmäki TSF: a tube sampler with a plastic tube and a flapper valve (A), a flow-through blade (B), and auger drill (C).

2.3.2. Flow-through blade

The flow-through blade method (Fig. 3B) uses a blade with a 0.4 m tube and openings that allow the sampled material to flow through as the blade penetrates the ground. Of the three methods, this is the least used at GTK in tailings investigations.

2.3.3. Auger drill

Auger drilling involves using a helical solid-flight screw (auger) to penetrate the sampled material (Fig. 3C). The auger drill was lifted on regular intervals and the material was sampled by scraping it off from the drill. With an auger sampler, a maximum of about 0.8 m of tailings sample weighting several kilograms can be obtained. In this study, a composite sample of about two kilograms was taken as a 0.5-meter sample, and two subsamples were combined to form a one-meter composite sample.

2.4. Laboratory analyses

The geochemical and grain size distribution samples were packed in a single pallet and submitted to ALS laboratory in Piteå, Sweden. All samples were dried at 60 °C (ALS Method DRY-22). For the geochemical samples, the standard scheme of crushing consisted of direct one-stage fine crushing to 85 % passing 2 mm (ALS Method CRU-31), and splitting using a Boyd crusher and rotary splitter combination (ALS Method

SPL-22Y). The samples were pulverized up to 250 g to 85 % passing 75 µm (ALS Method PUL-31). The devices were washed by inert quartz sand between each sample to minimize contamination. The grain size analysis was carried out by ALS Piteå (ALS Method SCR-61) and for inductively coupled plasma (ICP) fusion and optical emission spectrometry (OES) by ALS Loughrea, Ireland (ALS Method ME-ICP81).

The grain size distribution samples were wet screened to the fractions of <32 µm, 32–75 µm, 75–125 µm, 125–250 µm and 250–500 µm. The d50-values of the samples were determined by numerical calculation, utilizing an automated script in an Excel file. First, the script determined the two sieve sizes between which the cumulative percentage passing was 50 % (sieve sizes d1 and d2 with corresponding cumulative percentages p1 and p2). Then, linear interpolation to estimate the d50 value was used, with a formula:

$$d_{50} = d_1 + \frac{50 - p_1}{p_2 - p_1} \times (d_2 - d_1)$$

2.5. Database

The resource database for the Otanmäki tailings study was compiled into a Microsoft Access database, incorporating sampling results from both 2017–2018 and 2023 drilling campaigns ($n = 192$ drill points). The coordinate system used was ETRS-TM35FIN. The elevation was based on the local mine grid. Data sheets in the access database contained

information on the collar (drillhole location) and survey (drillhole path) of the sampling sites, assay results, and particle size data for the samples. The database contained assay data for 891 samples and particle size data for 470 samples. The original assay data was not altered or modified before being entered into the database, as no Fe, Ti or V values were below the detection limit. Validation of the database integrity was performed by a thorough check of the data and visual validation of the collar and survey data was checked to ensure that there are no errors in the spatial data. Differences in data inputs between the 2017–2018 and 2023 sampling campaigns are listed in Table 1.

Assay data was composited to a length of 1.0 m, following the most frequent sample length. Residuals at the ends of drillholes were discarded if their length was <0.75 m. The original total sample length for all the samples included in the study database was 496.55 m. The total composited sample length was 477.25 m (−3.9 % from the original sample length).

2.6. Modelling

In this study we tested the grade spatial variability at varying scales and with different sample data points to assess the sensitivity of sampling density to the resource modelling of the Otanmäki TSF and how the results can be reflected via estimation confidence in UNFC.

To study the effects of sampling densities on resource estimation results, a total of eight models on three different scales were created, each studied as a standalone scenario built using the same methodology (Table 2). The selected scales were 700 × 600 m, 300 × 300 m, and 100 × 100 m. A Model 0, using only data that was collected in 2017–2018 was created for each scale. 1–2 models containing new sample data were created per scale, each with different sampling densities to gain a range from sparse to moderate to dense sampling. To avoid uncertainties with the slope of the dam on the perimeter of the tailings area, blocks partially outside the tailings pond were discarded entirely. This is a conservative approach and may lead to slight underestimation of the tailings material in the 700 × 600 m models.

Variography for the different model scenarios was performed in Supervisor (Supplementary File 3). A spherical variogram and two structures were used for all modelling scenarios. The modelling parameters, for example variograms, were re-calculated separately based on each model scenario and assigned to a new block model. Block models for each case were constructed in Geovia Surpac 2022, where attributes for the modelling were created (Table 3), and the modelled area was constrained separately for each model using the same workflow (Fig. 4). The block models were angled at 30 degrees, to follow the orientation of the tailings area, the flow direction of the tailings material from the discharge outlet (Fig. 1), and the original sampling grid. At least three samples and a maximum of 30 samples were selected for informing the blocks. Models of each scale were constrained in the xy-plane by the area where the samples were taken into the model, extended past the final sample point by 50 m, 50 % of the previous drillhole spacing. Blocks that were only partially within the constraints were left out of the estimation results. The anisotropy ratios of the major and semi-major axes in the search ellipsoid were defined in the continuity models in the variograms for each model. The in-situ dry bulk

Table 1
Differences between the 2017–2018 and 2023 sampling campaigns.

	2017–2018	2023
Sampling method	Auger drill	Tube sampler
Sample length	0.8 m and 1.0 m	1.0 m
Sample length at bottom of hole <0,5 m	Taken as own sample	Combined with above sample
Assay method	Eurofins Labtium 720P	ALS ME-ICP181
Ti assay results	Ti, converted to TiO ₂ using stoichiometric constant (1.66806)	TiO ₂

Table 2

A summary list of data used in all eight models in this study.

Topographic control	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The surface of the tailings pond is the digital elevation model created with stereo photogrammetry from aerial images taken with a drone at a flight altitude of 120 m. The bottom of the tailings pond was modelled via triangulation from the end-of-hole points where the peat layer had been reached.
Location of data points	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The drill hole locations were pinpointed using differential GPS. All drillholes included were drilled to the bottom of the tailings material, where the basal structure is a peat layer.
Database	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data from the 2017–2018 and 2023 sampling campaigns are used in estimation, despite the differences in sampling methodology. The collected data is considered harmonized enough to be compiled into a single database.
Domaining	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No additional domaining performed; the resource estimates from the models are assumed to be from within one domain.
Density	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The dry bulk density used is 1.77 g/cm³, which was determined during the 2017–2018 sampling campaign.
Block model	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The block size for the models was 35 × 35 × 2 m with 17.5 × 17.5 × 1 m sub-blocking.

Table 3

List of attributes created for the block models for tonnage and grade calculations and model validation.

Attribute name	Data type	Decimals	Description
ands	Real	2	Anisotropic distance to nearest sample
aveands	Real	2	Average anisotropic distance to nearest sample
avetrds	Real	2	Average true distance to nearest sample
trds	Real	2	True distance to nearest sample
bv	Real	2	Block variance
kv	Real	2	Kriging variance
lg	Real	2	Lagrange multiplier
ke_TiO2	Real	2	Kriging efficiency TiO ₂
zz_TiO2	Real	2	Slope of regression TiO ₂
TiO2_krig	Real	2	TiO ₂ grade calculated by Ordinary Kriging
Fe2O3_krig	Real	2	Fe ₂ O ₃ grade calculated by Ordinary Kriging
V_krig	Real	2	V grade calculated by Ordinary Kriging
TiO2_idw	Real	2	TiO ₂ grade calculated by IDW
Fe2O3_idw	Real	2	Fe ₂ O ₃ grade calculated by IDW
V_idw	Real	2	V grade calculated by IDW
nn	Integer		Number of negative weights
numdh	Integer		Number of drill holes used to inform block
numsam	Integer		Number of samples used to inform block

density used was 1.77 g/cm³, based on the previous work of Hokka and Markovaara-Koivisto (2019) where it was determined using a volume-based method. The cut-off grade was set at 4-wt% TiO₂.

Ordinary Kriging was used to estimate the block model attributes for the 700 × 600 m models as well as the 300 × 300 m models. IDW (Inverse Distance Weighted) with isotropic search ellipsoid ratios were used for the 100 × 100 m models due to the low number of samples included yielding unreliable variography results. Results from variography informed the parameters that were used in the estimation, which was iterated several times with slight changes in parameters to achieve the best possible results in the final block model. Models with the highest high kriging efficiency values and high slope of regression (Z/Z* slope) values were selected. Visual validation was performed by comparing the block model grades compared to sample grades from the drillholes. Furthermore, swath plots were drawn from the models to validate if the trends in the input data are reflected in the model (Supplementary File 4). After the estimates were validated, tonnages and grades for TiO₂, Fe₂O₃ and V were calculated from the resultant block model. The grade results for each model were then compared statistically with the input sample data for another round of validation.

Fig. 4. The modelling workflow in the Otanmäki case study.

3. Results

3.1. Assay

At the Otanmäki TSF, the average drillhole depth reached a thickness of 6.9 m, ranging between 2.4 m and 9.4 m (Fig. 5). The water table was encountered at most sampling points, revealing a clear boundary between unsaturated and saturated zones, and varied between 0.5 m and

2.5 m. All samples were moist to varying degrees and contained occasional rock chips and larger fragments. The results of the grain size analysis (d50 mean = 138.47 μm) were as expected compared to the previous work in the area (Supplementary File 1) (Hokka and Markovaara-Koivisto, 2019).

The average concentrations for the 233 analysed samples collected during 2023 were 6.59 wt% for TiO₂, 21.42 wt% for Fe₂O₃ and 0.081 wt % for V (Table 4). A comparison of TiO₂, Fe₂O₃, and V grade values

Fig. 5. Two sampling profiles from the Otanmäki tailings area. (A) TiO₂ grades in the NW-SE sampling profile (view to 029) with easting coordinates. (B) TiO₂ grades in the SW-NE sampling profile (B, view to 299) with northing coordinates. The dashed line represents the topographic surface.

between the previous drilling campaign of 2017–2018 and the new data collected in 2023 is presented in Table 4 and Supplementary File 5. The Welch's *t*-test yielded a *p*-value of 0.975, indicating no statistically significant difference between the two groups. Thus, the grade values can be considered consistent across the two sampling periods and adequate to be combined into a single database.

No top cutting was applied to the data as assay results did not show any outliers. The input data for the different models were compared to determine that there is no clear bias in the sample selection for the models. Assay values for TiO₂, Fe₂O₃ and V are mainly normally distributed and with single grade population. There was no indication of bimodal distribution. The variography results showed a low nugget value in all cases, with ranges and anisotropy ratios showing variation with different sampling densities.

3.2. Sampling methodology comparison

The results between the three different sampling methodologies, tube sampler with a plastic tube and a flapper valve, flow-through blade and auger drill, display mostly similar results (Fig. 6) with only a few random outliers in the data across the three repeated drillholes. The average Fe₂O₃ concentrations in all the samples collected from the three test drill holes RH-169, RH-177 and RH-187 were 22.9 % for the tube sampler samples, 22.1 % for the flow-through blade samples and 23.3 % for the auger samples. The average TiO₂ concentrations were 7.7 % for the tube sampler samples, 7.2 % for the flow-through blade samples and 8.5 % for the auger samples. Samples collected with the auger drill resulted in some elevated Fe₂O₃ and TiO₂ especially at the very last samples of the holes (Fig. 6).

According to the observations during the field work, the method including the tube sampler with a plastic tube and a flapper valve performed well, and sample collection was successful even from water-saturated layers. The flow-through blade did not perform well in this study, as sample material fell off during the retrieval phase. In general, the auger drill method performed well and was relatively quick, but some contamination was noted by tailings material falling into the drill hole and by the material accumulating on the surface of the sampler from the walls of the sample hole during the sample retrieval phase.

Student's *t*-test for paired samples yields a *p*-value of 0.053 between the tube sampler and flow-through blade grade populations for TiO₂ and a value *p*-value of 0.079 between the tube sampler and auger grade populations. The mean of the flow-through blade grades is slightly smaller than with the tube sampler, and the mean of the auger grades are the highest. These results indicate that the differences between the methods are not statistically significant using a *p*-value of 0.05.

3.3. Modelling

The results for the model scenarios are shown in Table 5, and visualizations of three of the models are shown in Fig. 7. The selected cutoff for all resource estimates was 4 % TiO₂. Across all models, only a few

blocks did not have high enough grades to meet the selected cutoff.

In the 700 × 600 m Model 0 containing only data from 2017 to 2018, the tonnage was 4.71 Mt. with grades of 7.10 % TiO₂, 21.70 % Fe₂O₃, and 0.08 % V (Table 5). In the 700 × 600 m Model 1 containing also the new data from 2023, the tonnage was the same, and TiO₂ grade (6.9 %) and the Fe₂O₃ grade (21.60 %) were slightly less compared with the Model 0, −2.9 % and −0.5 %, respectively. The V grade was the same in both Model 0 and Model 1.

In the 300 × 300 m Model 0 containing only data from 2017 to 2018, the tonnage was 1.79 Mt. with grades of 6.80 % TiO₂, 21.10 % Fe₂O₃, and 0.08 % V. In the 300 × 300 m Model 1 containing also the new data from 2023, the tonnage was the same, and TiO₂ grade (6.7 %) was slightly less (−1.5 %), and Fe₂O₃ grade (21.20 %) slightly higher (+0.5 %) compared with the Model 0. In the Model 2 containing 2017–2018 data and five samples from the 2023, the tonnage was 1.80 Mt. and the grades for TiO₂, and Fe₂O₃ the same as in the Model 1. The V grade was the same in all the models.

In the 100 × 100 m Model 0 containing only data from 2017 to 2018, the tonnage was 0.51 Mt. with grades of 6.60 % TiO₂, 20.60 % Fe₂O₃, and 0.08 % V. In the 100 × 100 m Model 1 containing 2017–2018 data and four samples from the 2023, the tonnage was 0.47 Mt., and TiO₂ grade (6.2 %) was less (−6.5 %), and Fe₂O₃ grade (20.70 %) slightly higher (+0.5 %) compared with the Model 0. In the Model 2 containing 2017–2018 data and all the 2023 sample data, the tonnage was 0.47 Mt., and TiO₂ grade (6.2 %) was less (−6.5 %), and Fe₂O₃ grade (20.80 %) higher (+1.5 %) compared with the Model 0. The V grade was the same in all the models.

The swath plots drawn for validation indicated that there was some smoothing of the data in the models (Supplementary File 4). Swath plots were drawn in northing and easting directions, which were at an angle to the strongest trend in the data identified during variography (030) and the sampling grid. Each model was visually validated to ensure that there are no major discrepancies between the sample data and block data, an example of a NW-SE (direction 030) cross section of the 700 × 600 m Model 1 is presented in Fig. 8. The difference in block model grades to borehole grades ranged from 0.0 % to +4.7 % (Table 6).

4. Discussion

4.1. Sampling methodology test

Three sampling methods were evaluated within this study to assess the optimal approach for representative sampling. According to field observations, the auger drill enabled rapid drilling and facilitated the collection of large samples. The reason for consistently higher TiO₂ wt% values obtained from the auger drill is uncertain. Mixing of materials occurs as the sample is brought up through the hole, making the exact location of the sampled material uncertain. In certain conditions, material from higher strata can accumulate on the inner surface of the sampler, which may be difficult to detect. Additionally, sampling below the water table or within water-saturated layers presents challenges,

Table 4
Basic statistics for TiO₂, Fe₂O₃ and V for the 2017–2018 and 2023 samples.

	2017–2018			2023		
	TiO ₂	Fe ₂ O ₃	V	TiO ₂	Fe ₂ O ₃	V
Average	7.18 wt%	21.73 wt%	0.085 wt%	6.59 wt%	21.42 wt%	0.081 wt%
Median	6.91 wt%	21.45 wt%	0.084 wt%	5.99 wt%	21.00 wt%	0.080 wt%
Mode	5.55 wt%	21.59 wt%	0.083 wt%	5.37 wt%	20.20 wt%	0.80 wt%
Std deviation	1.756	2.002	0.007	1.906	1.965	0.008
Variance	3.085	4.01	0	3.634	3.861	0
Kurtosis	1.33	0.406	1.88	4.282	3.237	2.17
Skewness	0.89	0.564	0.91	1.98	1.302	0.89
Min	3.40 %	17.44 %	0.07 %	4.00 %	15.35 %	0.06 %
Max	14.73 %	29.31 %	0.12 %	14.90 %	29.60 %	0.11 %
Samples	287	287	287	233	233	233

Fig. 6. Repeat measurements of TiO_2 and Fe_2O_3 with the tube sampler, flow-through blade and auger sampling methods from the three triplet holes. (A) Results from the drillhole RH-169. (B) Results from the drillhole RH-177. (C) Results from the drillhole RH-187.

substantially increasing the risk of contamination. The tube sampler, equipped with a plastic tube and a flapper valve, proved effective in lifting samples from specific intervals, thereby reducing the risk of external contamination from the walls of the sample hole during retrieval. This method is ideal for shallow tailings; however, sample collection time increases considerably when drilling beyond a depth of 5 to 7 m.

Of the three sample collectors included in the study, the flow-through blade proved to be the least effective. Nevertheless, its performance could be improved by introducing a valve at the drill tip. The flapper valve used in the tube sampler also demonstrated reliability in slurry conditions, where the risk of contamination is high. It should be noted, however, that the flapper valve may result in the loss of approximately 5 cm of sample at the end if no material remains inside the valve. Based on the results of this study, it cannot yet be proven whether the flow-through method underestimates the grades at the ends

of holes or if the auger method overestimates the grades.

Overall, the differences in the results between the sampling methods show no statistical significance, despite different sample volumes. This is partly due to the homogeneous composition of the tailings at Otanmäki, as contamination from the upper walls had very little statistical significance with respect to TiO_2 wt% grade values. Due to the relatively dry drilling conditions at Otanmäki, down-the-hole contamination and cave-ins—resulting from tailings falling into the sample hole or material accumulating on the sampler's surface from the hole walls during retrieval—did not substantially affect the results (Fig. 6). This suggests that both the auger drill and the tube sampler with a flapper valve are suitable sampling methods at the Otanmäki site, as the tailings generally have low moisture content and exhibit reasonably good stability, minimizing the risk of cave-ins. However, the results might not apply to other tailings sites, as the overall sample quality depends on the sampled material and condition under which the samples are taken (Rossi and

Table 5

Resource estimates for the Otanmäki tailings area for the study areas of 700 × 600 m (Model 0 contains only data from 2017 to 2018 and Model 1 contains all of the data from the study area), 300 × 300 m (Model 0 contains only data from 2017 to 2018, Model 1 contains all of the data study area, and Model 2 contains the 2017–2018 data and five samples from the 2023 data) and 100 × 100 m (Model 0 contains only data from 2017 to 2018, Model 1 contains the 2017–2018 data and four samples from the 2023 data, and Model 2 contains all of the data from the study area).

Model	Tonnage	TiO ₂ grade	Fe ₂ O ₃ grade	V grade
700 × 600 m Model 0	4.71 Mt	7.10 %	21.70 %	0.08 %
700 × 600 m Model 1	4.71 Mt	6.90 %	21.60 %	0.08 %
Change	0.0 %	−2.9 %	−0.5 %	0.0 %
300 × 300 m Model 0	1.79 Mt	6.80 %	21.10 %	0.08 %
300 × 300 m Model 1	1.79 Mt	6.70 %	21.20 %	0.08 %
300 × 300 m Model 2	1.80 Mt	6.70 %	21.20 %	0.08 %
Change	0.0 %/+0.6 %	−1.5 %	+0.5 %	0.0 %/0.0 %
100 × 100 m Model 0	0.51 Mt	6.60 %	20.60 %	0.08 %
100 × 100 m Model 1	0.47 Mt	6.20 %	20.70 %	0.08 %
100 × 100 m Model 2	0.47 Mt	6.20 %	20.80 %	0.08 %
Change	−8.5 %/−8.5 %	−6.5 %/−6.5 %	+0.5 %/+1.0 %	0.0 %/0.0 %

Deutsch, 2014).

To summarise the test result for optimal sampling methodology at the Otanmäki TSF, the tube sampler was observed to be the most suitable of the different investigated sampling methods. According to the results of the comparison, the samples collected in 2017–2018 by the auger method are comparable to the tube sampler method used in 2023.

4.2. Spatial sampling density analysis

The modelling results indicated good grade continuity for TiO₂ at the Otanmäki TSF, supporting the conclusions of Hokka and Markovaara-Koivisto (2019). The main directions of anisotropy for the models were away from the discharge outlet of the tailings material (Fig. 1), perpendicular to the discharge direction, and vertical (Table 7). The variogram range increased with higher sampling density in the 700 × 600 m model but slightly decreased in the 300 × 300 m models (Table 8). As expected, larger model areas exhibited longer ranges. In this study, a global resource estimate for the entire tailings deposit was not conducted, as each model was treated as a standalone case, and sample information from outside the modelling area was excluded from the variograms. The ellipsoid orientations were horizontal, reflecting the flat nature of the tailings deposition. Grade continuity was also evident in the downhole variograms, although the vertical variogram range was limited by the tailings' depth, which is generally <10 m at the Otanmäki TSF. In contrast, horizontal variogram ranges were mostly between 100 and 200 m. The horizontal continuity directions aligned as expected: 1) along the flow direction away from the discharge outlet, which has been the source of the tailings material (Fig. 1), and 2) perpendicular to the flow direction, where material spread as the tailings pond widened.

The effect of adding sampling density on both the grades and tonnages is below ±10 % across all sampling densities and model sizes used in this study (Table 5). When comparing the 100 × 100 m Model 0, where the grade and tonnage are estimated from four boreholes to the 100 × 100 m Model 2, which covers the same area but uses information from 13 boreholes, the largest change in the studied elements is −6.5 % in TiO₂, despite more than tripling the number of boreholes used to

Fig. 7. Block models from the Otanmäki tailings area coloured by TiO₂ content with view to N with a plunge of 05 and a 10× vertical exaggeration. (A) Block model 700 × 600 m Model 1. (B) 300 × 300 m Model 1. (C) 100 × 100 m Model 1. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

inform the model. The largest changes in element contents in the larger modelling areas is even smaller; −1.5 % TiO₂ for both 300 × 300 m Models 1 & 2 when compared to the baseline Model 0, and −2.9 % TiO₂ for the 700 × 600 m Model 1 when compared to the baseline Model 0. This indicates that the previous 100 × 100 m grid of sampling used in 2017–2018 that covers the entire tailings pond, has been sufficient to estimate the grade and tonnage of the tailings material at a high level of confidence. Blannin et al. (2022) tested various sampling configurations and densities on the Davidschacht tailings facility, finding regular grids reduced tonnage variance, while random samples better captured spatial continuities. At higher densities, sampling configuration had little effect. However, they tested the sampling only on the 2 m surface layer of the tailings, with the assumption that the same rules would apply for samples at larger depth. Since the Otanmäki TSF was already sampled to a nominal grid of 100 × 100 m, we decided to add an even more densely sampled grid area to determine if a significant change in grade would occur within one cell of the sampling grid. The results indicate that for this case, there was no significant change. Additionally, single sample points were added within other cells of the 100 × 100 m grid to test if there are changes in spatial continuity, grade and/or tonnage and to gain coverage to test models at different scales. Again, the results indicated that no significant changes occurred in the grades and tonnages of the estimate, and the spatial continuity directions

Fig. 8. Example of a NW-SE (direction 030) cross section of the 700 × 600 Model 1 that was used for visual validation. (A) The block model with the TiO₂ assay data of drillholes. (B) The block model with TiO₂ grades within the blocks.

Table 6
Comparison of the difference between block model grades and borehole grades of TiO₂.

Model	Block model grade TiO ₂	Borehole grade TiO ₂	Difference
700 × 600 m Model 1	6.9 %	6.8 %	1.5 %
700 × 600 m Model 0	7.1 %	7.1 %	0.0 %
300 × 300 m Model 1	6.7 %	6.4 %	4.7 %
300 × 300 m Model 2	6.7 %	6.6 %	1.5 %
300 × 300 m Model 0	6.8 %	6.8 %	0.0 %
100 × 100 m Model 2	6.2 %	6.0 %	3.3 %
100 × 100 m Model 1	6.2 %	6.1 %	1.6 %
100 × 100 m Model 0	6.6 %	6.5 %	1.5 %

Table 7
Main anisotropy directions for the 700 × 600 and 300 × 300 models.

Model	Dir1	Dir2	Dir3
700 × 600 Model 0	040/00	130/00	130/-85
700 × 600 Model 1	030/00	120/00	000/-90
300 × 300 Model 0	345/-03	255/-04	295/85
300 × 300 Model 2	020/00	110/05	110/-85
300 × 300 Model 1	015/00	105/00	000/-90

remained unchanged. Additional samples were added as prongs emanating from the single densely sampled 100 × 100 m cell; the additional sample points could have been added as to each cell surrounding the central densely sampled cell, but some of the scale that we achieved by using our chosen sampling configuration would have been lost. In the end, a balance was struck between using the best sampling configurations suggested by Blannin et al., 2022, gaining the most sample coverage and having an area with high sampling density.

Table 8
Variography results for the 700 × 600 and 300 × 300 models.

Model	Type	Nugget	Structure	Sill	Range in DirI	Major	Minor
700 × 600 Model 0	Spherical	0.15	1	0.23	100	1.22	33.33
			2	0.62	137	0.307	19.57
700 × 600 Model 1	Spherical	0.05	1	0.17	152	0.688	152
			2	0.78	232	0.284	17.85
300 × 300 Model 0	Spherical	0.1	1	0.3	114	1.086	38
			2	0.6	181	0.588	45.25
300 × 300 Model 2	Spherical	0.15	1	0.1	96	0.667	33
			2	0.7	103	0.464	9.6
300 × 300 Model 1	Spherical	0.15	1	0.15	66	0.725	24
			2	0.7	98	0.711	14.71

4.3. Resource classification aspects (UNFC)

Our results in this study show minimal grade variability within different models scenarios and, thus, support high estimation confidence for the existing resource estimation model. The Otanmäki TSF is currently classified as E2; F2; G2 under the UNFC system (Eerola et al., 2024). According to UNECE (2019), the G2 category refers to “Product quantity associated with a project that can be estimated with a moderate level of confidence.” Our results showed less than a 10 % variation in grade and tonnage across all models in the investigated area. Typically, increasing sample density is expected to improve the accuracy and precision of the resource model and, therefore, affect grade and tonnage (Coombes, 2008). Our results support the homogeneous nature of the Otanmäki tailings deposit, where the material has been processed and deposited in a relatively uniform manner. As a result, significant variability in grade or tonnage is not expected, even with changes in sampling density or model scale. This suggests that the current estimation is relatively robust at the existing nominal sample density, providing high confidence results even at a more local scale. Consequently, it may be more appropriate to classify the deposit under the G1 category, which is defined as “Product quantity associated with a project that can be estimated with a high level of confidence” (UNECE, 2019), rather than G2. However, an updated global resource estimate of the Otanmäki TSF is required to reflect all the new conditions accurately for all domains. Tailings often present unique challenges for geostatistical modelling due to their complex depositional environments (Vick, 1970; Wilson et al., 2021; Blannin et al., 2023). Ordinary kriging provides a single smoothed estimate, suitable for general estimation but lacks insight into variability or uncertainty (e.g. Olea and Pawlowsky, 1996). Whereas, conditional simulation generates multiple realizations of the deposit, providing better insight into variability, uncertainty, and risk, especially in complex geological settings. Therefore, to better understand the spatial variability of the deposit more fully, conditional simulation should be tested.

Our approach helps to assess the overall confidence in the estimation, which can further support the classification of the Otanmäki TSF resource under the UNFC G-category. The UNFC classification was not determined for the entire tailings re-mining project, as this would require updated resource estimation from the entire TSF as well as detailed information on technical feasibility and the current project status concerning permitting and environmental aspects. In principle, this information is held by the mineral company. The focus was on G-category issues similarly as Eerola et al. (2024) discusses and clarifies the complexities involved in assessing the E-category of the UNFC.

4.4. Implications for other tailings projects

The conclusion that a 100 × 100 m sampling grid is sufficient might not be applicable to other types of TSFs with differing mineralogy and deposition method, especially at sites where tailings material has originated from separate ore deposits or varying ore types. The variability in grade and grain size within the Otanmäki TSF resulted in the creation of

three main domains resembling a delta-like deposition, with grain size and concentration varying by distance from the tailings outlet pipe (Fig. 1) (Hokka and Markovaara-Koivisto, 2019). The tailings material is moderately to well sorted and composed of mainly of ilmenite and silicates like hastingsite (Makkonen and Lavikko, 2018) which resulted in relatively good horizontal grade continuities and low nugget effect on all variograms. The area selected for this study represented only one of the several domains proposed by Hokka and Markovaara-Koivisto (2019), within one single grain size distribution, and was confirmed by the results of the grain size analyses.

The model should be supported by an adequate amount of accurate and precise data to reflect the true complexity of the geological ore deposit system being modelled. Uncertainty is inherent in resource models for both primary and secondary deposits, though the considerations may differ. Primary ore deposits are generally structure-controlled, exhibiting irregular continuities, with ore lenses that can vary in mineralogy—underscoring the importance of defining accurate domains (Coombes, 2008). In TSFs, emphasis should be placed on the fact that tailings are unconsolidated sands deposited through sedimentary-style processes (Vick, 1970; Robertson, 1994). Despite the greater accessibility of TSFs compared to primary deposits and the fact that tailings are primarily composed of processed residue, modelling still presents many uncertainties. These include the type of deposit, style of mineralization, processing history, and the technical and depositional history of the tailings, each of which must be considered individually, along with factors such as weathering, and metal leaching and mobilization (Sädbom and Bäckström, 2018). This information might not always be well documented or may be difficult to find for some historic and abandoned TSFs, requiring additional sampling and studies. To ensure that the collected data accurately represents the true complexity at manageable risk levels, a spatial sampling sensitivity analysis, such as the one performed in this study, is needed.

At the Otanmäki TSF, the tailings were discharged via a single stationary discharge outlet, which simplifies the sedimentation system. As TSFs are complex systems that require an understanding of the primary ore deposit type and mineralization style, combined with processing and waste disposal information and both primary and secondary depositional processes, tailings sites must always be investigated on a case-by-case basis. Sampling and modelling methodologies should always reflect the specific type of tailings deposit under investigation. At sites where tailings disposal practices vary over the life of the mine, the tailings heterogeneity can be substantially higher (Desbarats et al., 2024). Furthermore, minerals like ilmenite at Otanmäki, which constitute around 15 % of the total modal composition, are easier to sample and estimate due to their good continuity, compared to by-product quantities with trace-element contents. In TSFs where commercially valuable elements are present as trace quantities, most of the processed material is considered gangue. For example, at the Katherine Wash Au—Ag mine tailings, where resource potential was investigated by Karacan et al. (2023), the most elements of interest were distributed heterogeneously throughout the TSF and due to the high nugget effect, it is critical to ensure adequate sample volume and density. Therefore, the sampling

strategy should evolve gradually throughout the investigation, progressing from a baseline study to a more detailed study phase with iterations of modelling and assessing the uncertainty to see if more sampling is needed.

5. Conclusions

Based on the sampling conditions and the material being sampled, both the auger drill and the tube sampler with a flapper valve yield similar results under low moisture conditions at the Otanmäki TSF case site. However, the tube sampler was estimated to be more accurate and, therefore, more representative in varying conditions, despite having a smaller sample volume and being more time-consuming to use.

A spatial sampling sensitivity analysis, tailored site-specifically, is a useful strategy to improve confidence in the estimates prepared from a tailings project. It is a cost-effective approach than can be performed in a smaller area of the TSF to determine how much, if any, additional sampling is needed in the entire tailings area.

The Otanmäki TSF material is relatively homogenous, exhibiting good horizontal grade continuities and a low nugget effect, unlike some TSFs with grade heterogeneity and spatial complexity. Significant variability in grade or tonnage is not expected in the resource estimation, even with an increase in sampling density or changes in model scale. Denser sampling resulted in less than a 10 % change in grade and tonnage across all modelled scales and sampling densities tested in this study. Therefore, for the Otanmäki TSF, the bulk of the estimate can be regarded as having a high level of confidence in relation to the G-category in the UNFC.

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

Tuomas Leskelä: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Janne Hokka:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Teemu Karlsson:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Project administration.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Tuomas Leskelä reports financial support was provided by European Union. Janne Hokka reports financial support was provided by European Union. Teemu Karlsson reports financial support was provided by European Union. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data from 2023 samples available as Supplementary information. Data from 2017 to 2018 owned by Otanmäki Mine Oy and not publicly available.

References

- Blannin, R., Frenzel, M., Tolosana-Delgado, R., Gutzmer, J., 2022. Towards a sampling protocol for the resource assessment of critical raw materials in tailings storage facilities. *J. Geochem. Explor.* 236, 106974. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gexplo.2022.106974>.
- Blannin, R., Frenzel, M., Tolosana-Delgado, M., Büttner, P., Gutzmer, J., 2023. 3D geostatistical modelling of a tailings storage facility: resource potential and environmental implications. *Ore Geol. Rev.* 154, 105337. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oregeorev.2023.105337>.
- Coombes, J., 2008. *The Art and Science of Resource Estimation. Coombes Capability* (224 pp.).
- CRIRSCO, 2019. International reporting template for the public reporting of exploration targets, exploration results, mineral resources and mineral reserves. Available at: http://www.criresco.com/templates/CRIRSCO_International_Reporting_Template_November_2019.pdf.
- Desbarats, A.J., Beauchamp, M., Bilot, I., Polivchuk, M.J., Wyergangs, M., Percival, J.B., 2024. Critical mineral resource potential of tailings from the former Saint Lawrence columbium mine, Oka, Quebec. In: Geological Survey of Canada, Open File 9185. <https://doi.org/10.4095/pwu5neguzc> (53 pp.).
- Eerola, T., Solismaa, S., Karlsson, T., Hokka, J., 2024. Environmental and social governance issues of the Otanmäki (Finland) ilmenite tailings remining project. In: *Open File Research Report 56/2024* (20 pp.).
- European Commission, 2024. Critical Raw Materials Act. Viewed 21 10 2024. <https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/sectors/raw-materials/areas-specific-interest/critical-raw-materials/critical-raw-materials-act.en>.
- Hokka, J., Markovaara-Koivisto, M., 2019. Mineral Resource Estimate for Otanmäki Ilmenite Tailings Project, Finland.
- Illi, J., Lindholm, O., Levanto, U.-M., Nikula, J., Pöyliö, E., Vuoristo, E., 1985. Otanmäen kaivos. Vuoriteollisuus n:o 2, pp. 98–107 (in Finnish).
- Karacan, C.Ö., Erten, O., Martín-Fernández, J.A., 2023. Assessment of resource potential from mine tailings using geostatistical modeling for compositions: a methodology and application to Katherine Mine site, Arizona, USA. *J. Geochem. Explor.* 245, 107142. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gexplo.2022.107142>.
- Karlsson, T., Hokka, J., Kauppila, P.M., Tornivaara, A., Baldassarre, G., 2024. Potential of critical raw materials in closed Finnish mine waste sites: a preliminary review. In: *Proceedings of the ICARD 2024 – 13th International Conference on Acid Rock Drainage*, Halifax, Nova Scotia, Canada. Canadian Institute of Mining, Metallurgy and Petroleum.
- Lottermoser, B.G., 2011. Recycling, reuse and rehabilitation of mine wastes. *Elements* 7 (6), 405–410. <https://doi.org/10.2113/gselements.7.6.405>.
- Makkonen, H.T., Lavikko, S., 2018. Mineralogy of two samples from Otanmäki mine tailings pond. In: *Mineral Processing and Materials Research Outokumpu C/MT/2018/9*.
- Olea, R.A., Pawlowsky, V., 1996. Compensating for estimation smoothing in kriging. *Math. Geol.* 28, 407–417.
- Otanmäki Mine oy website, 2024. Extraction of valuable minerals from tailings pond. Available at: <https://www.otanmaki.fi/en/ilmenite-project/>.
- Puustinen, K., 2003. Suomen kaivosteollisuus ja mineraalisten raaka-aineiden tuotanto vuosina 1530–2001, historiallinen katsaus erityisesti tuotantolukujen valossa. In: *Report M 10.1/2003/3. Geological Survey of Finland*, 578 pp. (in Finnish).
- Robertson, W.D., 1994. The physical hydrogeology of mill-tailings impoundments. In: *Environmental Geochemistry of Sulfide Mine-Wastes*, pp. 1–17.
- Rossi, M.E., Deutsch, C.V., 2014. *Mineral Resource Estimation*. Springer, New York (331 pp.).
- Sädbom, S., Bäckström, M., 2018. Sampling of mining waste – historical background, experiences and suggested methods. [resource.sgu.se/produkter/regeringsrapporter/2018/RR1805-appendix2.pdf](https://www.sgu.se/produkter/regeringsrapporter/2018/RR1805-appendix2.pdf).
- Sarapää, O., Kärkkäinen, N., Al-Ani, T., 2015. High-tech metals in Finland. In: Maier, W. D., Lahtinen, R., O'Brien, H. (Eds.), *2015 Minerals Deposits of Finland*. Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-410438-9.00023-6> (792 pp.).
- Smeets, B.W., Bloom, L., Arne, D., Heberlein, D., 2024. Practical applications of quality assurance and quality control in mineral exploration, resource estimation and mining programs: a review of recommended international practices. *Geochem. Explor., Environ., Anal.* 24. <https://doi.org/10.1144/geochem2023-046>.
- Suppes, R., Heuss-Abichler, S., 2021a. Resource potential of mine wastes: a conventional and sustainable perspective on a case study tailings mining project. *J. Clean. Prod.* 297, 126446. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.126446>.
- Suppes, R., Heuss-Abichler, S., 2021b. United Nations Framework Classification for Resources Case Study – Base Metal Tailings Storage Facility Bollrich, Germany. *ECE/ Energy/GE.3/2022/14*, 28 pp. Available at: https://unece.org/sites/default/files/2022-05/ECE_ENERGY_GE.3_2022_14.pdf.
- United Nations Commission for Europe, 2019. United Nations framework classification for resources update 2019. In: *ECE Energy Series No. 61*, 20 pp. Available at: http://s://unece.org/DAM/energy/se/pdfs/UNFC/publ/UNFC_ES61_Update_2019.pdf.
- United Nations Commission for Europe, 2022. UNFC Guidance Europe: Guidance for the Application of the United Nations Framework Classification for Resources (UNFC) for Mineral and Anthropogenic Resources in Europe, 53 pp. Available at: https://www.unece.org/sites/default/files/2022-05/UNFC_Guidance_Europe_2022.pdf.

- [:/unece.org/sites/default/files/2022-11/UNFC%20GUIDANCE%20EUROPE-FINAL.pdf](https://unece.org/sites/default/files/2022-11/UNFC%20GUIDANCE%20EUROPE-FINAL.pdf).
- United Nations Commission for Europe, 2024. Bridging Document Between the Committee for Mineral Reserves International Reporting Standards Template and the United Nations Framework Classification for Resources. ECE/ENERGY/GE.3/2024/5, 20 pp. Available at: https://unece.org/sites/default/files/2024-04/CRIRSCO_Template_UNFC_BD_ECE_ENERGY_GE.3_2024_5_ENG.pdf.
- Vick, S.G., 1970. Planning, Design, and Analysis of Tailings Dams. BiTech Publishers Ltd., Vancouver, B.C. Canada <https://doi.org/10.14288/1.0394902> (1990, 381 pp.).
- Wilson, R., Toro, N., Naranjo, O., Emery, X., Navarra, A., 2021. Integration of geostatistical modeling into discrete event simulation for development of tailings dam retreatment applications. Miner. Eng. 164, 106814. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mineng.2021.106814>.